

Assessing Courses of the Online Learning Agreement

2.3 Questionnaire exchange students

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This document contains the set-up for the evaluation questionnaire for exchange students. The questions are based on:

- The desk study which includes a literature review and interviews with four teachers of exchange students;
- An open-ended questionnaire with teachers and coordinators (44 respondents) of universities in Europe to gather input on the transversal and course-specific requirements;
- Knowledge and experience with setting up questionnaires, evaluations and monitors at Risbo, Erasmus University Rotterdam;
- Input from our test panel consisting of students who filled in the questionnaire and provided feedback;
- And last but not least, input from our partners involved with the work package including AUTh, ELTE, ESN and EUF.

The document is set-up in the following way:

- Each page starts with the page number between brackets. This means that in the questionnaire, a new page needs to be 'opened'.
- The type of question is stated each time. It's either an open-ended question (indicated by a text box), a closed question (single choice or multiple choice), or statement questions rated on a 5-point Likert Scale.
 - Some single/multiple choice questions have an option 'other, namely'. This should be accompanied by an open-ended answer option.
- Each topic has a Title (purple) and an accompanying text (between brackets). This must be shown in the questionnaire.
- Suggestions for the tool in which the questionnaire will be taken, is part of the 'Online Tool Functionalities' report.

[page 1]

Background information

1. What best describes your gender?

- a) Female
- b) Male
- c) Non-binary
- d) A gender not listed here [open-ended question]
- e) Unsure how to describe myself
- f) Prefer not to say

2. What is your age?

3. Which host university do you study at? [folded-out list of universities to choose from]

4. What is the title of the course you are currently filling in this evaluation for?

5. Which home university do you study at? [folded-out list of universities to choose from]

6. What study are you following at your home university?

Note: questions 3 and 4 might be able to be retrieved from OLA and can then be left out from the questionnaire.

[page 2]

General impression of the course

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about your general impression of the course.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The overall quality of the course was sufficient	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course was well organized	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course subject matter was adapted to my prior knowledge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course objectives were clear to me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The relevance of the topics of this course within the context of my field of study was clear to me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The learning management system was clearly structured*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* The learning management system is the online environment that is used to share course details, course content and communications with you.

[page 3]

Learning methods, activities and set-up of the course

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about the learning methods, activities and set-up of the course.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The lectures of the course were adding to my understanding of the topic(s)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The activities in the course motivated me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The activities in the course prepared me for my future employment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The activities in the course helped me reflect on current societal challenges	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I understand how I can apply the course materials in a practical setting	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The number of social interactions with students in the course was sufficient	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The study load was evenly distributed throughout the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[page 4]

Teacher(s)

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about the teacher(s) of the course.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The teacher(s) of the course was/were approachable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were enough contact moments with the teacher(s) (office hours, lectures)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The teacher(s) provided opportunities to discuss difficulties / questions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The teacher(s) was able to deal with specific needs I had as an exchange student	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The teacher(s) taught in a motivating manner	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The teacher(s) showed interest in international perspectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Cultural differences/issues

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about the cultural differences and/or issues of the course.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Input from an international perspective was valued in the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The course provided me with opportunities to share my thoughts and feelings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The learning activities allowed for contact with other local/exchange students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I experienced no cultural obstacles in the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I experienced no language obstacles/barriers in the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

1. Optional: Please share your experiences with the cultural differences or issues you encountered in the course.

Type your answer

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Satisfaction with assessment methods and outcomes

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about your achievements and satisfaction of the course. This relates to the assessment methods and the outcomes of the course.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Details of the assessment(s) were communicated to me before the start of the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The actual assessment(s) were like what was communicated beforehand	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The assessment(s) represented the subjects discussed in the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The assessment(s) was/were applied fairly with attention to cultural differences of the students	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am satisfied with what I've learned during the course	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Evaluation methods within the course

[text] Please indicate whether you agree or disagree with the following statements about the evaluation methods within the course. This relates to the way the course is evaluated verbally or written and how many times your feedback on the course is being asked.

[likert scale scoring]

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The course is sufficiently evaluated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There was enough room to share my thoughts about the course with the teacher(s)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The timing of the evaluations was fitting	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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Concluding questions

1. What are your main motives to participate in this course? (multiple answers possible) [multiple options question]

- a) Academic opportunities
- b) Experiencing different cultures
- c) Career advancement
- d) Quality of education
- e) Personal motives
- f) Other, namely [open ended]

2. What are you most satisfied with regarding the course? (multiple answers possible) [multiple options question]

- a) The set-up/design
- b) The learning materials
- c) The learning activities
- d) The support of teachers
- e) The assessment(s)
- f) The lectures
- g) The content
- h) Interaction with students
- i) Other, namely [open ended]

3. Optional: Explain what you liked or disliked from the course.

Type your answer

4. Would you advise other exchange students to join this course?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) Not sure
- d) Other, namely [open ended]

5. Please explain why you would or wouldn't advise other exchange students to join this course.

Type your answer

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Final question

- 1. Are there any other personal thoughts and experiences as an exchange student you would like to share with us?**

Type your answer

[End questionnaire]

